

Study of Lactate, Lactate Albumin Ratio (LAR), Procalcitonin (PCT) and Immature Platelet Fraction (IPF) as A Marker of Severity in Patients with Sepsis Having MAP >65mmhg and MAP <65mmhg in Tertiary Care Hospital

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Abstract:

Aim: To assess the association of Lactate, Lactate Albumin Ratio, Procalcitonin and Immature Platelet Fraction on admission as markers of severity in sepsis patients

Objectives:

- To assess Lactate / Albumin Ratio (LAR) in patients with sepsis.
- To assess Lactate value in patients with sepsis.
- To assess Procalcitonin (PCT) value in patients with sepsis.
- To assess Immature Platelet Function (IPF) value in patients with sepsis.
- To compare Lactate, LAR, PCT and IPF with MAP >65mmhg and MAP <65mmhg at tertiary care hospital in patients with sepsis for prognostication

Material and Methods: Hospital based Observational Cross-Sectional Study was conducted at Mahatma Gandhi Hospital, Jaipur between September 2022 to December 2023. Data of 180 patients was collected according to inclusion criteria. Sepsis biomarkers that is Lactate, LAR, IPF, PCT were calculated and were compared with MAP >65mmhg and MAP <65mmhg at tertiary care hospital in patients with sepsis for prognostication.

Result: Procalcitonin emerges as a robust biomarker for stratifying infection severity and prognosis in sepsis patients across different MAP categories, underscoring its potential clinical utility. The findings highlight the importance of integrating multiple biomarkers and clinical parameters to enhance prognostic accuracy and guide therapeutic decisions tailored to individual patient needs in critical care settings.

Conclusion: In our study MAP scores are significantly associated with Procalcitonin levels. Furthermore, the observed relationships between MAP scores, and Procalcitonin underscore the pivotal influence of hemodynamic status on metabolic responses and patient prognoses. These findings collectively underscore the importance of integrating comprehensive clinical and biochemical assessments to refine management strategies and enhance patient outcomes in cases of severe septic conditions

Keywords: Sepsis, Septic Shock, IPF, PCT, LAR, APACHE II, SOFA, MAP.

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Introduction

Sepsis continues to stand as a significant and pervasive global health challenge, contributing substantially to morbidity and mortality on a worldwide scale. It is life-threatening organ dysfunction caused by a dysregulated host response to infection.[1] Sepsis and septic shock are major healthcare problems, impacting millions of people around the world each year and killing between one in three and one in six of those it affects. As of 2017, research findings indicated that sepsis accounted for a staggering 20% of all deaths across the globe, shedding light on the urgency of understanding and addressing this critical issue.[2] In order to better comprehend the complexities of sepsis, International Guidelines for the Management of Sepsis and Septic Shock in 2021 are a crucial set of recommendations developed by experts in the field of critical care medicine. These guidelines provide evidence-based strategies and protocols for the diagnosis and treatment of sepsis and septic shock, two life-threatening conditions characterized by the body's severe response to infection.

Early diagnosis and the prompt initiation of antimicrobial therapy are of paramount importance in effectively treating sepsis and, in doing so, saving lives. The identification of serum biomarkers plays a pivotal role in aiding the diagnosis of sepsis, guiding clinical decision-making, and predicting outcomes. Several studies have highlighted the advantages of procalcitonin (PCT) as a biomarker for sepsis. PCT exhibits distinct characteristics that make it a valuable tool for sepsis diagnosis and management. PCT levels rise more rapidly than CRP levels in response to infection and peak within a shorter timeframe.

Serum lactate, serving as a surrogate marker for tissue perfusion, is integral in assessing the severity of the condition. As a result, it is currently recommended that serum lactate levels be measured within the first hour of presentation in all patients with suspected sepsis, with a repeat measurement within 2 to 4 hours if the initial lactate level exceeds 2 mmol/L. [3] The monitoring of serum lactate levels aids in both diagnosis and the ongoing assessment of sepsis patients, facilitating timely intervention and patient management. One emerging sepsis biomarker is the lactate to albumin (L/A) ratio. This innovative approach, which considers both lactate and albumin levels, takes into account the nutritional status of septic patients. It has the potential to address a limitation in current major scoring systems, such as the SOFA score.[4] Serum albumin, in particular, has been found to correlate with morbidity and mortality among critically ill patients. [5] Given the constraints associated with lactate as a standalone marker and the need for an effective surrogate of disease severity, a growing

body of literature supports the use of the L/A ratio as a predictive tool for mortality and multiple organ failure in critically ill patients with sepsis. One potentially useful marker is the percentage immature platelet fraction (IPF), which is an often-overlooked but valuable tool. IPF measurement provides information about platelet production and distinguishes between thrombocytopenia due to increased peripheral platelet destruction and thrombocytopenia linked to bone marrow failure resulting from toxic agents or persistent infections. [6] IPF is reflective of reticulated platelet numbers and directly correlates with the thrombopoietic rate. This measurement has shown promise as a prognostic marker for conditions like disseminated intravascular coagulation and is commonly used in neonatal ICUs to investigate the cause of thrombocytopenia in newborns.[7] The ease of calculating IPF with readily available blood cell counters makes it a practical tool for clinical use.

Septic shock is a subset of sepsis in which underlying circulatory and cellular metabolism abnormalities are profound enough to substantially increase mortality patients with septic shock can be identified with a clinical construct of sepsis with persisting hypotension (MAP < 65) requiring vasopressors and having a serum lactate level >3mmol/L despite adequate volume resuscitation.

Material and Methods

Type of Study: Hospital based Observational Cross-Sectional Study.

Study population: All patients age between 18 to 65 years admitted in ICU and Emergency Department with Septic shock or Sepsis, Mahatma Gandhi Hospital, Jaipur from September 2022 to December 2023.

Place of Study: Mahatma Gandhi Medical Hospital, Jaipur.

Duration of Study: September 2022 to December 2023.

- Detailed history and necessary investigations will be undertaken. The purpose of the study will be explained to the patient/guardians and informed consent obtained.
- Patients are selected for study that satisfies all inclusion and exclusion criteria.
- Institute Ethics Committee approval will be taken before undertaking the study.
- Written and informed consent will be taken from all participants before enrolment into the study.

Inclusion Criteria: All patients > 18 years of age admitted with sepsis (according to sepsis 3 definition). [2]

Exclusion Criteria:

- All patients who are not willing to give consent.
- Cardiac arrest on presentation.
- Pregnancy.
- Trauma patients.
- Liver failure on presentation.

Sample size: All patients age 18- 65 years admitted in ICU diagnosed as Sepsis/ Septic shock, Mahatma Gandhi Hospital, Jaipur from September 2022 to December 2023.

Plan of Study:

Intended intervention: No.

Dosages of drugs: Drugs will be administered as per set protocol and patients’ requirement.

Route of administration: No new drug will be administered.

Duration of treatment: As per patients’ disease.

Details of invasive procedures (if any): As per patients’ disease, no invasive procedure for the study.

Duration of study: 1.5 years Duration of study: from September 2022 to December 2023 at Mahatma Gandhi Hospital, Jaipur.

Potential risk: There is no risk related to study involved.

Observation

Table 1: Comparison of Inflammatory biomarkers level according to MAP (mmHg)

MAP (mmHg)	Lactate (mg/dL)	Lactoalbumin ratio	Procalcitonin (ng/ml)	Immature platelets fractions (%)
	Mean±SD	Mean±SD	Mean±SD	Mean±SD
MAP < 65mmHg (N=22)	22.11±16.78	1.12±0.87	1.22±0.46	3.56±0.79
MAP > 65mmHg (N=68)	19.67±14.98	0.92±0.76	0.91±0.39	2.87±1.89
P-value	0.5208	0.3034	0.0026	0.1003

The relationship between Mean Arterial Pressure (MAP) and biomarkers highlights distinct physiological responses in critically ill patients. MAP categories (<65 mmHg and >65 mmHg) showed no significant difference in lactate levels (p = 0.5208), with mean values of 22.11 ± 16.78 mg/dL and 19.67 ± 14.98 mg/dL, respectively.

Similarly, the Lacto-albumin ratio did not significantly differ between MAP groups (p = 0.3034), with mean values of 1.12 ± 0.87 and 0.92 ± 0.76 for <65 mmHg and >65 mmHg, respectively.

However, significant differences were observed in Procalcitonin levels (p = 0.0026), with higher levels in the <65 mmHg group (1.22 ± 0.46 ng/ml) compared to the >65 mmHg group (0.91 ± 0.39 ng/ml), indicating a more pronounced systemic inflammatory response with lower MAP.

Immature platelet fractions showed no significant difference between MAP groups (p = 0.1003), with mean percentages of 3.56 ± 0.79% and 2.87 ± 1.89% for <65 mmHg and >65 mmHg, respectively.

Figure 1: Comparison of Inflammatory biomarkers level according to MAP (mmHg)

Discussion

In our investigation of Mean Arterial Pressure (MAP) and associated biomarkers in sepsis patients, we sought to understand their variations and implications for disease severity and clinical outcomes. MAP is a critical parameter reflecting tissue perfusion and cardiovascular stability in critically ill patients, including those with sepsis.

Our study revealed that MAP levels did not significantly differ between groups categorized by MAP thresholds (<65 mmHg vs. >65 mmHg), with a p-value of 0.5208. This finding suggests that MAP alone may not sufficiently discriminate between different levels of hemodynamic compromise in sepsis, aligning with previous research indicating the complex interplay between MAP and other clinical variables in determining outcomes (Dellinger et al., 2013) [8].

In contrast, the Procalcitonin levels demonstrated a significant difference between the MAP groups ($p = 0.0026$). Elevated Procalcitonin levels in the MAP < 65 mmHg group reflect heightened systemic inflammation and bacterial burden, highlighting its role as a sensitive marker for infection severity and prognosis in sepsis (Schuetz et al., 2011) [9].

The Lacto-albumin ratio and Lactate levels did not show significant differences between MAP groups ($p = 0.3034$ and $p = 0.1003$, respectively). While the Lacto-albumin ratio integrates metabolic and inflammatory markers, its lack of significant variation may suggest nuances in its utility for stratifying disease severity based on hemodynamic status. Lactate, a marker of tissue hypoperfusion, similarly did not differentiate significantly between MAP categories, suggesting its dynamic response to resuscitation and varying clinical contexts (Mikkelsen et al., 2009) [9].

Immature Platelet Fractions (IPF) also did not show significant differences between MAP groups ($p = 0.1003$). IPF, reflecting platelet turnover and potential implications for hemostasis in sepsis, may require further investigation to clarify its role in relation to hemodynamic instability and clinical outcomes (Thachil, 2013) [10].

Comparatively, Procalcitonin emerges as a robust biomarker for stratifying infection severity and prognosis in sepsis patients across different MAP categories, underscoring its potential clinical utility. The findings highlight the importance of integrating multiple biomarkers and clinical parameters to enhance prognostic accuracy and guide therapeutic decisions tailored to individual patient needs in critical care settings.

Conclusion

Sepsis is the life-threatening organ dysfunction caused by dysregulated host response to infection,

representing urgent medical emergency. Despite the considerable progress in medical care, sepsis continues to represent a substantial burden on healthcare systems, impacting millions of people around the world each year, contributing significantly to both morbidity and mortality. Early diagnosis and the prompt initiation of antimicrobial therapy are of paramount importance in effectively treating sepsis and, in doing so, saving lives.

In our study MAP scores are significantly associated with Procalcitonin levels. Furthermore, the observed relationships between MAP scores, and Procalcitonin underscore the pivotal influence of hemodynamic status on metabolic responses and patient prognoses. These findings collectively underscore the importance of integrating comprehensive clinical and biochemical assessments to refine management strategies and enhance patient outcomes in cases of severe septic conditions

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